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Students' Listening Comprehension By Using English Breaking News

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to determine listening comprehension using Breaking News English in third semester English students at Khairun University, Ternate. This research uses quantitative descriptive methods, this research involves 25 participants, research instruments use tests and documentation. The results obtained from the Listening Skills Test were that 16 students out of 25 students in the class were able to answer the questions very well. Research findings regarding listening comprehension showed that, of the 25 students, 16 (64%) were in the "very good" category, 4 (16%) were in the "Good" category, 2 (8%) were in the "fair" category. good category". "category", 3 (12%) are in the "low" category. Third semester English students have an average listening comprehension score of 88.48 which means they are classified as "Very Good". From these results it can be concluded that the listening comprehension of third semester English students at Khairun University using Breaking News English was categorized as very good.

Keywords : *Listening Comprehension, English Breaking News*

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INTRODUCTION

Listening comprehension is about developing skills in a foreign language, listening is the first skill that needs to be taught to students at the school and university levels because listening is one of the skills that are difficult for students to understand if not heard well. Listening is an active process that aims to understand what we hear. But in reality, students always find it difficult to listen well because sometimes they feel bored and not interested in the lesson.

In line with the statement above, Cahyono (2018) argues that listening is a language skill that is difficult for students to master. Regarding the difficulties faced by students, listening needs to be taught creatively by the teacher. Teaching listening is almost related to practice, which can motivate students to improve their listening skills. The significance of listening is also due to its role in providing language input to learners in the forms of language use such as the use of vocabulary, grammar, and discourse. Teachers can develop listening comprehension by using methods that can make it easier for students to improve their listening skills, in a practical way such as visual learning styles for spoken texts that are associated with students' minds with pleasant reactions, one of which is by using video programs on TV or YouTube such as English breaking news.

In this way it can make students interested in increasing their listening comprehension. They can provide realistic view American culture and motivate learners to enhance their comprehension (Burt in Ramawati.R (2016). Therefore, breaking news is one of the real resources that can be used because it provides students with attention-grabbing visual and audio content. Through watching TV news broadcasts, students could simultaneously learn the speaker's tone, new vocabulary, accent, facial expression, and body language. To ensure that the students fully grasp the subject, TV news programs must be used as teaching resources in listening lessons.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. The Definition of Listening Comprehension

According to Tyagi in Zohra et.al (2019), Listening is a language modality, it is considered one of the four basic skills of language, listening, speaking, reading, and writing. The four language skills students studying the English language are required to acquire. Listening is the most frequent form of

communication in daily life." we can expect to listen twice as much as we speak, four times more than we read, and five times more than we write." (Morley, 1991). One of the language knowledge that students find hard to learn is listening. Due to the challenges that the students confront, the teacher needs to creatively teach listening. Learning to listen is somewhat like exercise, which might inspire students to get better at it. Listening does not represent a simple word-by-word translation but involves understanding a deeper meaning.

According to Rivers (2006), Listening is a creative skill, which means we understand the sound that falls on our ears and take the raw material of words, strings of words, and the rise and fall of sounds, and from this material, we are creative in significance. The listener must cope with the sender's choice of vocabulary, structure, and level of delivery. Rost in Gilakjani et.al (2016), Defined listening comprehension as an interactive process in which listeners are involved in constructing meaning. Listeners comprehend the oral input through sound discrimination, previous knowledge, grammatical structures, stress and intonation, and other linguistic or non-linguistic clues. According to Sissons in Liza et.al (2013), The news is created. What we see, hear, and read is just a version of events that has been crafted and shaped by the people assembling the newspaper, radio, or television bulletin.

2. Media of Listening Skill

The word "media" describes a resource used to inform students. The word "media" is derived from the Latin word "medium," which means "middle, intermediate, or introduction." It is the plural form of that word. Sadiman et al. (2010) claim that "media is an intermediary or messenger" between the message's sender and recipient. In the area of media education, media education is referred to as the method by which teachers communicate with students. According to Sadiman et al. (2014) the media is everything that is used to transmit messages from the sender to the recipient so that it can stimulate the thoughts, feelings, attention and interest of students in such a way that the learning process occurs.

3. Concept of English News Program

The most challenging component of training in English hearing is news English because of its distinctive structure and linguistic qualities. According to Suparyo et al, (2011). Asserts that one advantage of radio and television is that they speak to the individual rather than the general public Flemming (2006). Avoid using long sentences and unusual vocabulary in broadcast news; instead, speak naturally.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses a quantitative descriptive. According to Bryman (2001), is research that emphasizes numbers and numbers in data collection and analysis. Arikunto (2006) defines a quantitative descriptive research approach as something that starts with data collection, data interpretation, as well as appearances and findings, with the aim of building an objective picture or description of a situation using numbers. This study aims to determine whether using audio-visual media (latest news in English) has improved students' listening comprehension. This research is conducted at campus of the faculty of teacher training and education at Khairun University for students in the English education department.

The researchers do a number of acceptable procedures, including tests and documentation, to gather the data required for this investigation. Descriptive quantitative research is the method by which researchers gather their research data. In order to collect quantitative data, the researcher adds the student's English listening exam results. The researcher attached the students' results from the English listening test, which was given through English News, in order to collect quantitative data. The methods utilized by researchers to gather data are as follows: testing and documentation.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The findings of this research consist of a classification of listening test results from students of the third semester English study program, teaching and educational sciences faculty at Khairun University. This aims to find answers to research questions. In this test, researcher tested students' listening skills by playing breaking news English (BBC) videos.

Table 2. Data Of Listening Test Result

No	Respondent	Number Of Correct Answer	SCORE	Category
1	ESU	23	92	Very Good
2	P	20	80	Good
3	PAS	20	80	Good
4	NS	20	80	Good
5	AMT	11	44	Low
6	HG	17	68	Fair
7	SM	16	64	Fair
8	SU	15	60	Low
9	SRAN	21	84	Very Good
10	S	21	84	Very Good
11	N	23	92	Very Good
12	MP	18	72	Good
13	NI	22	88	Very Good
14	PW	22	88	Very Good
15	NLB	22	88	Very Good
16	NL	10	40	Low
17	RRY	23	92	Very Good
18	SN	21	84	Very Good
19	PRAK	23	92	Very Good
20	SMU	21	84	Very Good
21	S	21	84	Very Good
22	YSH	23	92	Very Good
23	MG	23	92	Very Good
24	NATI	23	92	Very Good
25	AU	22	88	Very Good
Total	N=25		2.004	

The student listening ability test score data is classified as follows: Sixteen (16) students obtained the highest scores in the test range (84, 88, and 92). which is classified as very good; Four (4) obtained range scores (72 and 80). which is classified as good; two (2) students obtained range scores (64 and 68). which is considered sufficient; three (3) students who got a range of scores (40, 44 and 60) got the lowest scores. This shows that the listening skills of third semester students are quite good because most of the students got the highest marks.

Table 3. Listening Comprehension Test Category Result

NO	Listening Skill Test Category	Number of Correct Answer	Amount of Students	Classification	Percentage
1.	Very Good (81-100)	23	7	Students are very able to understand the context being discussed and give the correct answer with the right vocabulary.	28%
		21	5		20%
		22	4		16%

2.	Good (71-80)	20	3	Students are able to understand the context being discussed but do not know the vocabulary in English to answer.	12%
		18	1		4%
3.	Fair (61-70)	17	1	Students are less able to understand the context discussed and give wrong answers	4%
		16	1		4%
4.	Low (0-60)	10	1	Students misunderstood the context being discussed and gave the wrong answer.	4%
		11	1		4%
		15	1		4%
Total		25 Questions	25 Students		100 %

From the results of the category obtained from the listening comprehension test is 16 students (64%) are categorized as very good, because they are able to understand the context being discussed and provide the correct answer with the right vocabulary. Respondents who were able to answer 23 questions correctly as many as 7 students (28%) got the highest score of 92. Respondents who were able to answer 21 questions correctly 5 students (20%) received a score of 84. and 4 students (16%) could answer 22 Questions correctly and get a score of 88.

From the results of the category obtained from the listening comprehension test is 6 students (16%) are categorized good, because students can understand the context being discussed but do not know the English vocabulary to answer it. There are 3 students (12%) who can answer 20 questions correctly and get a score of 80. And 1 student (4%) can answer 18 questions correctly and get a score of 72. From the results of the category obtained from the listening comprehension test is 2 students (8%) categorized as fair, because it misunderstands the context discussed and gives the wrong answer. 1 student (4%) can answer 16 questions correctly and get a score of 64. 1 student (4%) can answer 17 questions correctly and get a score of 68. From the results of the category obtained from the listening comprehension test is 3 students (12%) are categorized as low, because students who are less able to understand the context being discussed and provide wrong answers. 1 student (4%) can answer 10 questions correctly and get a score of 40. 1 student (4%) can answer 11 questions correctly and get a score of 44. And 1 student (4%) can answer 15 questions correctly and get a score 60. A total of 16 students out of 25 students in the class were able to answer the questions very well. Research findings regarding listening comprehension revealed that, of the 25 students, 16 (64%) were in the "very good" category, 4 (16%) were in the "Good" category, 2 (8%) were in the "fair" category, 3 (12%) falls into the "low" category. Third semester English students have an average listening comprehension score of mostly 88,48 which means they are classified as "Very good".

The results of this research are in line with the results of Rahmawati's research (2016), namely "Improving Listening Comprehension Using TV News Programs". Who found that students' listening comprehension using TV news programs could improve students' listening comprehension and also increase students' active participation during the learning process. Authentic materials are believed to improve listening because learners learn spoken English from a real communication environment. Authentic video including films, TV news programs, and news broadcasts. according to Harmer (2010) in Rahmawati (2016) Listening skills are also good for our students' pronunciation. The more they hear and understand spoken English, the more they absorb the correct tone and intonation, stress and sound of words as well as words combined together in connected speech. The results of this

research are in line with Liza et.al (2013), namely "The Ability of UNP English Department Students in Listening to English News" which found that English students have quite good listening comprehension skills in responding to information using English news. This means that using English news can improve students' abilities, influenced by the teaching methods applied in large numbers of exercise. According to Sissons (2006) in Liza et.al (2013), news on radio and television conveys the latest and most important news to viewers and listeners. Listening to English news is good for students for several reasons. First, for academic purposes, training to listen to English news from various sources, fields, materials, accents and dialects, will help them understand listening material from various sources, fields, materials, accents and dialects. This also contradicts other relevant research previously conducted by Ikhsan (2021)", namely An Analysis on Students' Listening Comprehension Problems at The Third Semester English Language Education Of Islamic University Of Riau. and the results show that the problem that often occurs among students is a lack of mastery of foreign language vocabulary and it becomes difficult for them to understand the context being discussed. Thus, based on these conditions, it is necessary to pay attention to the learning background obtained by students. This refers to problems where students misunderstand the context being discussed. This correlated with opinion of Butt (2010) reported that the major problem hindering listening comprehension was that the students' vocabulary was too limited to understand the message. Of the three previous researchers, in this study the researcher only conducted one test to access students' listening comprehension.

CONCLUSIONS

It is found that students involved in research on student listening comprehension tests using Breaking News are categorized as very good which means that the students are very able to understand the context being discussed and provide correct answers with the right vocabulary in listening comprehension. It can be seen that 16 students got the highest scores out of 25 students in the class, and several other students got quite good scores to lower grades. Many students get high scores because they are able to understand the context being discussed, while students who get low scores because they lack vocabulary mastery in English still find it difficult to understand foreign language pronunciation and lack understanding of the context being discussed.

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